

Exposure of Non-Target Terrestrial Plants (NTTPs) via plant protection product spray drift in the current regulatory EU framework

The “realistic worst-case scenario” as the basis for a “one-size-fits-all” risk assessment

Exposure of Non-Target Terrestrial Plants (NTTPs) via plant protection product spray drift in the current regulatory EU framework

The “realistic worst-case scenario” as the basis for a “one-size-fits-all” risk assessment

Deposition

Basic drift values for one application
Ground sediment in % of the application rate (90th percentiles)

Distance [m]	Field crops	Fruit crops		Grapevine		Hops	Vegetables Ornamentals Small fruit	
		early	late	early	late		Height < 50 cm	Height ≥ 50 cm
1	2,77							
3	0,95	29,20	15,73	2,70	8,02	19,33	0,95	8,02
5	0,57	19,89	8,41	1,18	3,62	11,57	0,57	3,62
7	0,29	11,81	3,60	0,39	1,23	5,77	0,29	1,23
15	0,20	5,55	1,81	0,20	0,65	3,84	0,20	0,65
20	0,15	2,77	1,09	0,13	0,42	1,79	0,15	0,42
30	0,10	1,04	0,54	0,07	0,22	0,56	0,10	0,22
40	0,07	0,52	0,32	0,04	0,14	0,25	0,07	0,14
50	0,06	0,30	0,22	0,03	0,10	0,13	0,06	0,10
75	0,04	0,11	0,11	0,015	0,05	0,04	0,04	0,05
100	0,03	0,06	0,06	0,009	0,03	0,02	0,03	0,03
125	0,025	0,03	0,04	0,007	0,024	0,01	0,025	0,024
150	0,02	0,021	0,03	0,005	0,018	0,006	0,021	0,018
175	0,01	0,024	0,004	0,014	0,004	0,004	0,018	0,014
200	0,01	0,019	0,003	0,011	0,003	0,016	0,011	0,011
225	0,01	0,016	0,003	0,010	0,002	0,014	0,010	0,010
250	0,01	0,013	0,002	0,008	0,001	0,012	0,008	0,008

Rautmann et al. (2001). New basic drift values in the authorization procedure for plant protection products. Workshop on Risk Assessment and Risk Mitigation Measures (WORMM) Vol. 13. 3-141.

Deposition refers to the settling of droplets mostly due to gravity. -> this is Rautmann

Capture

Capture focuses on the interception of airborne spray droplets by the intended target (e.g., plants).

There is currently little information about the spray drift capture efficiency of NTTPs.

First Insights into Drift Capture Efficiency of Non-Target Terrestrial Plants

Rena Isemer¹, Andrew C.
Chapple¹, Clare Butler Ellis²,
Andrew Lane², Christine
O`Sullivan²

¹ Bayer AG

² Silsoe Spray Applications Unit Ltd

May 14, 2025

SETAC Europe Conference 2025 in Vienna

Four different plant species selected to represent different growth forms and surface structures.

- tall
- broad leaves
- hairy

- medium size
- medium sized leaves
- waxy cuticula

- grass
- thin leaves

- small
- broad leaves
- little hair

Single Plants set-up in the SSAU wind tunnel

Stainless steel rods as standardized collectors for comparison

 steel rod

- wind speeds: 1 m s⁻¹ and 2 m s⁻¹
- nozzle: F110-03 at 3 bar
- boom: 0.6 m height, 10 km h⁻¹
- 142 L ha⁻¹ under the boom
- distances downwind plants/collectors: 1, 3 and 5 m
- “Green S” dye
- deposit on plants expressed as μL tank mix per g plant fresh weight
- airborne spray concentration derived from the quantity deposited on rods per unit cross-sectional area

Single plants capture a lot of drift at 1 m distance with a rapid decline with distance (approximately 7-fold at 3 m, 25-fold at 5 m).

Further experiments done at 3 m down-wind distance and 2 m/s wind speed

Deposition on single plants differed according to the tested species (soy, oats, oilseed rape similar quantities; sunflower lower quantity).

Block set-up

Depending on species, capture efficiency was reduced approximately by a factor of 2–5 in the middle of the blocks.

Conclusion

- // **Preliminary** investigation indicated that **capture efficiency of plants depends on the species**, having size, shape and structure as one of the main influencing factors.
- // Plants **directly next to the field** will catch the **highest amount of drift**, just some centimeters **inside the canopy** the captured drift is **much lower**.
- // Results support the assumption that the effect of spray drift on (not only) NTTP adjacent to treated fields is currently dealt with in a very **simplified way** in the regulatory system.
- // **Further wind tunnel and realistic field experiments** as well as modelling would allow for a more realistic risk assessment approach but require a **better understanding of the capture efficiency of NTTPs**.

Data on capture is used...

...to develop/validate models which...

...deliver exposure values.

Mechanistic drift model that predicts airborne spray,
e.g. Casanova Drift Model, SiMod

+

Model capable of predicting capture, e.g. CFD

NTTP RA

effects / exposure
= TER > threshold

3.03.C.T-02 3D spray drift exposure data for non-target terrestrial organism risk assessment

Carola Schriever¹, Clare Butler Ellis², Andrew Lane², Christine O'Sullivan², Lindsay Fogg³, Nadine S Taylor⁴ and Neil Mackay⁵, (1)BASF SE, Germany, (2)Silsoe Spray Applications Unit Ltd, United Kingdom, (3)Cambridge Environmental Assessments, United Kingdom, (4)Cambridge Environmental Assessments, Boxworth, United Kingdom, (5)FMC Agro Ltd., United Kingdom

- // Results support the assumption that the effect of spray drift on (not only) NTTP adjacent to treated fields is currently dealt with in a very **simplified way** in the regulatory system.
- // **Further wind tunnel and realistic field experiments** as well as modelling would allow for a more realistic risk assessment approach but require a **better understanding of the capture efficiency of NTTPs**.

Health for all, Hunger for none

Thank
you!

bayer.com

Looking forward to meeting you at the Bayer Booth (43-44)

Altering wind-profile*, changed capture efficiency for some species.

* with an up-wind baffel, so the wind speed is lower at the plants level not at the boom level